

ELIXIR-ENA data service

The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) provides a comprehensive open record of the world's nucleotide sequencing information and a platform for the management and analysis of sequence and related data. ENA is designated by the ELIXIR infrastructure both as a Core Data Resource, and a Deposition Database.

Services

ENA's portfolio of services include user support (helpdesk, training), web sites (data submissions, browser with search, explore and download functions), RESTful interfaces (data submissions, data discovery, metadata interrogation) and a host of downloadable utilities to support data submissions and access.

Current federation

EMBL-EBI (EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute) has released a Swagger 2.0-based API for discovering metadata about available studies. ELIXIR-ENA "study" level records are mapped to the Blue-Cloud first level metadata records.

Function in Blue-Cloud

The ENA system contains many data types / classes and a huge volume of data, which are only partly marine-related. ENA stands to benefit from the Blue-Cloud project because the project allows it to connect to all these different data types and allows scientists to access in an interdisciplinary way all these data.

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